

Effect of Simplifications of Core Analysis Model on Neutronics Characteristics of HTTR

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluates the impact of simplifying the detailed core structures in the HTTR analysis model on reactivity. Using the continuous-energy Monte Carlo code MVP, we compared the nuclear characteristics of a detailed core analysis model and a simplified model. The simplified model is commonly employed in deterministic methods. The modeling focused on in this analysis was the side shielding blocks, top shielding blocks, and control rods. For the simplifications, the side and top shielding blocks were replaced with helium with a vacuum boundary condition at the outer surface. The control rods were modeled with axially uniform sleeves and neutron absorbers, while disregarding shock absorbers. The k_{eff} from the detailed model aligns with the benchmark values within experimental and benchmark uncertainty, confirming the validity of the detailed model. We found that the simplifications in the side and top shielding blocks resulted in approximately -0.007 to 0.02 $\% \Delta k/k$ differences, while the simplification of control rods caused a maximum difference of about -0.09 $\% \Delta k/k$, which would not be negligible.

Keywords: HTGRs, core analysis model, HTTR, MVP3, neutronics characteristics

1. INTRODUCTION

High-Temperature Gas-Cooled Reactors (HTGRs), known for their high inherent safety, are gaining attention as next-generation nuclear reactors, with operational testing planned for the late 2030s in Japan [1]. For the core design and safety analysis of these demonstration reactors, deterministic analysis codes are likely to be used due to computational load considerations. However, HTGRs exhibit unique structures, such as coated fuel particles and graphite structural materials, thus the physical phenomena are considerably different from those of conventional light water reactors. As a result, existing deterministic analysis codes, primarily developed for light water reactors, cannot adequately handle these phenomena. To address this challenge, the development of a new deterministic analysis code capable of appropriately handling the nuclear characteristics of HTGRs is underway [2-4]. For validating the developed code, the Very High-Temperature Reactor Critical Assembly (VHTRC) [5], which has abundant criticality experiment data, and the High-Temperature Engineering Test Reactor (HTTR) [6], which has accumulated operational data, are envisaged as benchmark facilities. Due to the complex structures in these systems, it is challenging to model them accurately using deterministic methods, necessitating the use of simplified core analysis models. However, the effects of these simplifications on nuclear characteristics are not well quantified.

Previous international benchmark analyses [7-9] utilized reactor physics test data collected during the startup of HTTR to validate the computational accuracy of continuous-energy Monte Carlo codes. Furthermore, in a previous study [10], an analysis was performed using the latest nuclear data library with a core analysis model, e.g., reference [7]. These analyses only considered the influence of core instrumentation on reactivity effects arising from the simplifications in the core analysis model adopted in international benchmark analyses. The impact of other simplifications, however, has not been evaluated.

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In this study, we utilized the latest nuclear data library JENDL-5 [11] and a continuous-energy Monte Carlo code capable of detailed modeling to create a detailed core analysis model for the HTTR. We analyze how the anticipated simplifications in core structures for future deterministic analysis code affect the effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}). Here, the effects of simplification were evaluated for three components with complex geometries: the side shielding blocks, top shielding blocks, and the control rods. Details of the modeling are described in Section 2.

This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the detailed core analysis model of HTTR. Section 3 outlines the analysis methodology and the calculation cases. Section 4 confirms the validity of the developed core analysis model and discusses the impact of simplifications applied to each structure. Finally, Section 5 presents the conclusions and plans.

2. CALCULATION MODELS

2.1. HTTR Whole Core

In this study, we analyzed the initial core of HTTR, with a focus on the core configurations described in HTTR-GCR-RESR-001 [7] and HTTR-GCR-RESR-003 [9]. Figure 1 shows a radial cross-section of the core analysis model developed for this study. In this model, the permanent reflector located at the core periphery was modeled as a regular dodecagonal prism with a side-to-side distance of 4,250 mm and a height of 5,250 mm. Additionally, the outermost section of the core is modeled as a reactor pressure vessel (RPV) made of 2-1/4Cr-1Mo steel, with an inner diameter of 5,500 mm and a thickness of 122 mm, with a vacuum boundary condition applied to its outer surface. Actual fuel blocks and control rod guide blocks contain handling holes used during fuel replacement operations. They also contain dowel pins and dowel sockets used for alignment purposes. However, these components are not explicitly modelled in this study or the international benchmark analysis model. Instead, the graphite density is reduced by 0.5%.

Figure 1. Radial cross-section of the fully loaded core HTTR.

2.2. Shielding Block

2.2.1. Side shielding block

The actual structure and analysis model of the side shielding block are shown in Figure 2-(1) [7] and (2). The side shielding block is installed radially outward from the permanent reflector block, with a coolant path separating them. The side shielding block is primarily composed of a SUS316 casing and neutron absorbers (B_4C/C). Although detailed information on the dimensions was not publicly available, we assumed that the side shielding block consists of half casing and half neutron absorber, based on Fig. 2-(1). In Fig. 2-(2), we modeled the part closer to the permanent reflector as a 49 mm thick neutron absorber, and the outer part as a 49 mm thick casing. The coolant path is set at 43.6 mm width.

Core support structures, such as support legs and restraint bands, are not included in this analysis model and have been replaced with helium.

Figure 2. Actual structure (1) [7] and analysis model (2) of side shielding block.

2.2.2. Top shielding block

The actual structure and analysis model of the top shielding block are shown in Figure 3-(1) [7] and (2). Like the side shielding block, the top shielding block consists of an SUS316 casing and neutron absorbents (B_4C/C), located at the top of each column. Detailed dimensions are not publicly available; however, we assumed its structure is identical to that of the graphite block directly below it, based on the continuity of the coolant flow path and the perspective of control rod insertion. The neutron absorber is partially enclosed within the casing, with the lower half mainly consisting of the neutron absorber and the upper half primarily of the casing. In Fig. 3-(2), the height of the top shielding block is set at 30 mm, which is the difference between the height of the permanent reflector (5,250 mm) and the fuel column (5,220 mm). Here, based on Fig. 3-(1), the height of the top shielding block seems to be approximately 200 to 300 mm. However, in this study, the height of the top shielding block was set to 30 mm based on the published overall dimensions. The side-to-side distance is 360 mm. The height of control rod guide columns is 100 mm shorter than the other columns, so the height of the top shielding block in that region was set to 130 mm.

Figure 3. Actual structure (1) [7] and analysis model (2) of top shielding block.

2.3. Control Rod

The actual structure and analysis models of the control rod (CR) are shown in Figure 4-(1) [7], (2), and (3). HTTR control rods are inserted through the CR insertion holes of diameter 123 mm and are

composed of ten neutron absorber sections and a shock absorber. Each section is interconnected by a spine, with slight gaps present between sections. The sleeve has a thickness of 3.5 mm and a double cylindrical structure with an outer diameter of 113 mm and an inner diameter of 65 mm. Each of the ten sections has a neutron absorber height of 290 mm, resulting in a total stack length of 3,100 mm, including the gaps between sections. In this analysis, we created two models: the CR detailed model (2), which incorporates shock absorbers and accounts for slight gaps between sections, and the CR simplified model (3), which removes the shock absorbers and assumes uniform absorbers and sleeves along the axial direction. In Fig. 4-(2), the height of each section is assumed to be 305 mm, and the gaps between sections are set at 5 mm. Furthermore, it is assumed that gaps between the sleeve and neutron absorber are filled with helium. In Fig. 4-(3), these gaps are not considered. The shock absorber, modeled with a height of 55 mm and an inner diameter of 86 mm, is composed of the Alloy-800H that is the same as the sleeve. When inputting the critical rod position, the upper end of the shock absorber is positioned at the measurement location.

Figure 4. Actual structure (1) [7] and analysis model of control rod (2), (3).

3. ANALYSIS METHOD

For this analysis, the continuous-energy Monte Carlo code MVP3 [12] is used. Additionally, JENDL-5 was employed for the nuclear data library. For the thermal scattering law (TSL) data, graphite with ideal crystals (0% porosity) was adopted [13], and the thermal cutoff energy is set to 30 eV [14]. Each batch consisted of 50,000 histories, with 5,000 active and 1,000 inactive cycles. The core temperature was assumed to be uniform. In the HTTR-GCR-RESR-001 [7] core, room temperature (300 K) condition is applied, while in the HTTR-GCR-RESR-003 [9] core, elevated temperature (400 and 420 K) conditions are applied. CRs are positioned at the critical rod position. The k_{eff} is calculated using the following four models (models A to D):

- Detailed model without simplifications of CRs and shielding blocks. The axial vacuum boundary condition is set outside the top shielding blocks and the bottom replaceable reflector. Radially, the vacuum boundary condition is set outside the RPV.
- Simplified model with the top shielding blocks removed. The axial vacuum boundary condition is set outside the top replaceable reflector, with all other conditions remaining the same in model A.
- Simplified model with the side shielding blocks and the RPV removed. The radial vacuum boundary condition is set outside the permanent reflector, with all other conditions remaining the same in model A.
- Simplified model using the CR simplified model. The other models including the external boundary condition are the same as model A.

At first, we compared the k_{eff} of model A with the benchmark values [7], [9]. The benchmark values were obtained by correcting the measurement value with the reactivity effect of reactor instrumentation and temperature. Furthermore, we compared them with the analysis results of [7], [9], and [10]. Next, we compared the k_{eff} of model A with those of models B to D to confirm the impact of simplification of each structure on reactivity.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1. Comparison with Benchmark Values and Previous Analyses

Figure 5 shows the analytical results of k_{eff} for model A and those from previous analyses [9,10], compared against the benchmark values [7,9]. In Fig. 5, the blue error bars correspond to the experimental uncertainties of the benchmark values, while the smaller error bars on the square and triangle markers indicate the statistical uncertainties by the MVP calculations. The experimental uncertainties, which include contributions from measurement errors in temperature and control rod positions, as well as uncertainties in dimensions and material impurities, are reported as ranging from -0.0060 to $+0.0071$ at 300 K, -0.0057 to $+0.0068$ at 400 K, and -0.0057 to $+0.0067$ at 420 K [7,9]. The statistical uncertainties (1σ) of the MVP calculations were from ± 0.00005 to ± 0.00011 . It should be noted that the analyses in Ref. [10] using JENDL-5 and ENDF/B-VIII.0 employed the TSL data for ideal crystal graphite (0% porosity), which is consistent with the present analysis. The analytical results for model A are in good agreement with the benchmark values within their uncertainties at all temperatures, with the differences ranging from approximately $-0.21\% \Delta k/k$ to $-0.06\% \Delta k/k$. This indicates that the analysis using model A is appropriate. On the other hand, analyses using conventional analytical models (benchmark models) such as those in Refs. [9,10] show differences of approximately $1.49\% \Delta k/k$ to $1.73\% \Delta k/k$ from the benchmark values, and differences of about $1.79\% \Delta k/k$ from the results of model A. These differences will be discussed further in Section 4.2.

Figure 5. Benchmark values and analysis result for model A and [9], [10].

4.2. Impact of Model Simplification

Figure 6 shows the reactivity effects of the model simplifications. The reactivity difference, $\Delta\rho$, is calculated using the k_{eff} of model A (k_A) and models B to D ($k_{B,C,D}$) as follows:

$$\Delta\rho = \frac{k_{B,C,D} - k_A}{k_{B,C,D} \cdot k_A} \quad (1)$$

Additionally, assuming the statistical errors of k_A and $k_{B,C,D}$ are σ_A and $\sigma_{B,C,D}$, respectively, the error of $\Delta\rho$, $\sigma_{\Delta\rho}$, is estimated based on the following error propagation:

$$\sigma_{\Delta\rho} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_A}{k_A^2}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{B,C,D}}{k_{B,C,D}^2}\right)^2} \quad (2)$$

A comparison between model A and models B to D revealed that reactivity differences were approximately 0.005 % $\Delta k/k$ to 0.02 % $\Delta k/k$ for the side shielding blocks and -0.004 % $\Delta k/k$ to 0.02 % $\Delta k/k$ for the top shielding block. In contrast, a larger difference of approximately -0.09 % $\Delta k/k$ to -0.07 % $\Delta k/k$ was observed for the CRs. From these results, it was concluded that the impact of simplifying the side and top shielding blocks is negligible, whereas the simplification of the CR analysis model considerably affects the reactivity. The CR simplified model, when compared to the CR detailed model, has an increased amount of neutron absorber due to the neglect of gaps between each section, while simultaneously having a decreased amount of neutron absorption from the omission of the shock absorber. The results shown in Figure 6-(3) are understood to be a consequence of the combination of these competing effects.

Figure 6. Effect of simplification of each structure on reactivity.

Here, we discuss the differences between the results obtained with the detailed model developed in this study and those from previous research that utilized the international benchmark model. Among the calculated reactivity differences, only the presence or absence of the shielding blocks could explain the difference between the analytical results of the detailed model and the benchmark model. The impact of the shielding blocks simplification is estimated to be at most approximately 0.03 % $\Delta k/k$ according to Fig. 6-(1) and (2), indicating they are not a major contributor to the observed differences between the models. Therefore, identifying the causes of these differences is a subject for future investigation.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Toward a future validation of a deterministic neutronics code for HTGRs, this study investigates the effects of simplifying core structures on the k_{eff} using the continuous energy Monte Carlo code MVP3 with the latest nuclear data library JENDL-5. Specifically, the reactivity effects of simplifying the side and top shielding blocks, as well as the detailed structure of CRs in the HTTR, were analyzed.

Four analytical models were considered: model A, a detailed model without simplifications of the shielding blocks or CRs; model B, a simplification model where the top shielding blocks were replaced with helium; model C, a simplification model where the side shielding blocks were replaced with helium; and model D, a simplification model where the CR neutron absorber and sleeve were axially simplified, and the shock absorber was removed. Comparing the results of model A with those of models B to D allows the effects of simplifying the top shielding blocks, side shielding blocks, and CRs to be evaluated individually.

The analysis results for model A showed good agreement within the uncertainty range with the benchmark values provided by the International Reactor Physics Experiment Evaluation Project (IRPhEP), confirming the validity of this analysis model. However, when compared with previous analysis results using the international benchmark model, differences of approximately 1.79 % $\Delta k/k$ were observed.

The impacts of simplification for each structure were approximately 0.005 % $\Delta k/k$ to 0.02 % $\Delta k/k$ for the side shielding blocks, -0.004 % $\Delta k/k$ to 0.02 % $\Delta k/k$ for the top shielding blocks, and approximately -0.09 % $\Delta k/k$ to -0.07 % $\Delta k/k$ for the CRs. These results indicate that the simplification of the CR analysis model has the most significant influence on reactivity. However, the effects of the structural simplifications considered in this analysis could not fully explain the differences observed between the present detailed model and the previous analyses. Investigating the cause of these differences remains a future task.

As other future research topics, the annular core of the HTTR will be analyzed in future work. The effects on axial and radial reaction rate distributions will also be analyzed. Additionally, we plan to evaluate the impact of burnable poison modeling and the effects of simplifications of the core analysis model on burnup calculations.

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REFERENCES

- [1] "The Basic Policy for the Realization of GX: Reference Document," Accessed: Oct. 09, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://www.meti.go.jp/english/press/2023/pdf/0210_003c.pdf
- [2] J. Y. CHO et al., "Improvement and Verification of the DeCART Code for HTGR Core Physics Analysis." *Nucl. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 51, no. 1, pp. 13–30, Feb. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.net.2018.09.004.
- [3] A. Yamamoto and G. Chiba, "Verification of Neutronics Analysis Method using CBZ and GENESIS for a Prismatic High-Temperature Gas-Cooled Reactor," In *Proc. PHYSOR 2024*, San Francisco, CA, USA, Apr. 21–24, 2024, pp. 1572–1580, doi: 10.13182/PHYSOR24-43456.
- [4] K. Yamaji et al., "Resonance Treatment of Double-Heterogeneous Fuel Using a Deterministic Statistical Geometry Method in Heterogeneous Transport Calculation Code GALAXY-Z," *Nucl. Sci. Eng.*, Oct. 2024, doi: 10.1080/00295639.2024.2397259.
- [5] H. Yasuda et al., "Construction of VHTRC (Very High Temperature Reactor Critical Assembly)," JAERI, Tokai, Ibaraki, Japan, JAERI 1305, Aug. 1987, doi: 10.11484/jaeri-1305.
- [6] S. Saito et al., "Design of High Temperature Engineering Test Reactor (HTTR)," JAERI, Tokai, Ibaraki, Japan, JAERI 1332, Sep. 1994, doi: 10.11484/jaeri-1332.
- [7] J. D. Bess and N. Fujimoto, "Evaluation of the Start-Up Core Physics Tests at Japan's High Temperature Engineering Test Reactor (Fully-Loaded Core)," OECD/NEA, Paris, France, NEA/NSC/DOC(2006)1 HTTR-GCR-RESR-001 CRIT-SUB-REAC-COEF-KIN-RRATE, Mar. 2010.

- [8] J. D. Bess and N. Fujimoto, "Evaluation of the Start-Up Core Physics Tests at Japan's High Temperature Engineering Test Reactor (Annular Core Loadings)," OECD/NEA, Paris, France, NEA/NSC/DOC(2006)1 HTTR-GCR-RESR-002 CRIT-REAC-RRATE, Mar. 2010.
- [9] J. D. Bess N. Fujimoto, "Evaluation of Zero-Power, Elevated-Temperature Measurements at Japan's High Temperature Engineering Test Reactor," OECD/NEA, Paris, France, NEA/NSC/DOC(2006)1 HTTR-GCR-RESR-003 CRIT-COEF, Mar. 2011.
- [10] P. H. Liem, "The Application of JENDL-5.0 Covariance Libraries to the Keff Uncertainty Analysis of the HTTR Criticality Benchmark," *J. Nucl. Eng.*, **vol. 6**, no. 2, Article no. 11, Apr. 2025, doi: 10.3390/jne6020011.
- [11] O. Iwata et al., "Japanese Evaluated Nuclear Data Library Version 5: JENDL-5," *J. Nucl. Sci Technol.*, **vol. 60**, no. 1, pp. 1–60, 2023, doi: 10.1080/00223131.2022.2141903.
- [12] Y. Nagaya et al., "MVP/GMVP Version 3: General Purpose Monte Carlo Codes for Neutron and Photon Transport Calculations Based on Continuous Energy and Multigroup Methods," JAEA, Tokai, Ibaraki, Japan, JAEA-Data/Code 2016-2018, Mar. 2017, doi: 10.11484/jaea-data-code-2016-018.
- [13] K. Ramic et al., "Assessing Criticality Implications of Small Angle Neutron Scattering and Porosity Misrepresentation in ENDF/B-VIII.1 TSLs for Nuclear Graphite," In *Proc. PHYSOR 2024*, San Francisco, CA, USA, Apr. 21–24, 2024, pp. 1527–1538, doi: 10.13182/PHYSOR24-43635.
- [14] S. Takeda et al., "Investigation of Thermal Cutoff Energy for Accurate Analysis of High Temperature Engineering Test Reactor," *ASME J. Nucl. Rad. Sci.*, **vol. 11**, no. 4, pp. 040904-1–6, Aug. 2025, doi: 10.1115/1.4067755.